

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM (HEMIS) IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

In contemporary world the usage of Learning Management Systems (LMS) plays a vital role particularly in foreign language learning and teaching. One of the widely used LMS is HEMIS which stands for Higher Education Management Information System. It has been used in higher education system for over 3 years. This work includes survey results which was held in Nukus State pedagogical institute in order to know the attitude of students towards implementation of HEMIS in foreign language learning and teaching. The outcome of the survey states that this education management system is practical and potentially beneficial.

The modern labor market requires workers to be professionally competent, ready constantly improve your professional results and personal qualities. The market economy emphasizes the need for skilled workers who are competitive in the labor market and meeting the modern requirements of employers. Modern system of professional education should take into account processes of globalization in society, constant changes in technologies, the importance of effective interaction between education and the labor market, changes in the social life of the country and the need continuing professional education. This should contribute to regular renewal content of education and professional training of qualified competitive workers in accordance with the requirements national and regional labor markets. These goals, in turn, require a change in the organization work in institutions of professional education. Playful forms of the learning process through an online portal become possible with the help of learning management systems known as LMS (Learning Management System). As a platform for e-learning LMS means the following: Learning With an LMS, you create a single database of e-courses and learning materials. Management -LMS can manage the courses, and can learners. To start training, just add students and assign them courses. System -An electronic system. Being in different cities, you can train everyone who wants to, without leaving your own office. In addition, the LMS automates the work of checking tests, collecting statistics and preparing reports. Learning through an LMS does not have to be done remotely[2, 2-3]. It is necessary to introduce new pedagogical ideas, pedagogical technologies, forms and methods of training, organization of work and

management institutions. Therefore, it is extremely important to create an innovative educational environment and use innovative pedagogical technologies for the formation professional competencies of future employees of vocational education institutions. Education is the most important factor in the development of modern society, since its content, quality and improvement contribute to solution of acute problems of mankind [5, 61-63]. For ensuring the progressive development of society in areas of digital technologies, it is necessary to train personnel who are able to freely use digital technologies. For this, information educational environments are needed, which provide the possibility of acquiring skills to use digital technologies (technical and software funds). An information and educational system is defined as a system based on a hybrid intelligence with the predominant use of various technical means and processing techniques information; open pedagogical system, aimed at the formation of a creative, socially and intellectually developed personality[4, 4043-4048]. Under the influence of information and communication technologies, a qualitatively new information learning environment (ILE) as a set of conditions that ensure the interaction of users with information resources, information interaction with other users based on interactive ICT tools [3, 34-48]. In modern educational institutions platforms for distance education are widely used. Information system HEMIS provides e-learning services for administration staff, teachers and students at the expense of automation of the main activities of higher educational institutions. Information system serves as an information bridge between higher educational institutions and the Ministry higher and secondary specialized education and serves to refuse the paper form of information, received from higher educational institutions, and digitization of the management system. Carol Fallon defines learning management system as a Web-based software that allows managing and doing necessary studies to monitor the use of educational content and its results. Although he believes that different systems have different features, these features can be classified in two general categories: -Management functions such as adjusting the course, learner registration, allocation of the course and reporting of student progress based on data such as grades, final and interim period facilities, time spent on the course, and the final status upon completion of the course. - The intersection of learner includes a page where by using ID and password, the learner enters LMS, so that through a menu or specific page have access to educational content that is dedicated to him and understand the status of his progress according to test scores [1, 45-56]. Implementation of feedback of the subjects of the educational process is one of the strongest sides of HEMIS. The system supports file sharing of any format - both between the teacher and the student, and between the students themselves. Newsletter service allows you to promptly inform all course participants or separate groups about current events. Forum technology gives opportunity to organize training discussion of problems, while the discussion can be carried out as groups, as well as with all course participants. Users can attach files of any formats. The system is equipped with the function of evaluating messages - both teachers and students. The necessity for excellent language pedagogy approaches is created by numerous entities. Implementation of education management systems is being looked at more and more as a way to fill the resource gap that many institutions are currently experiencing in order to provide students with a solution for language instruction. Learning management systems can be used

to support teaching and learning, as well as to reach and inspire students with special needs. Students who reside in rural or distant places or who have limited access to authentic resources and opportunities to interact with the target language and culture should place a specific emphasis on this component of LMS. HEMIS has attracted a lot of interest from ESL and EFL professionals. Many instructors and professionals have chosen to use HEMIS in their second- and foreign-language classrooms. As its system for managing courses across the entire university, Nukus State pedagogical institute has chosen HEMIS. Institutions and universities can publish their course schedules and assignments, host online conversations, administer quizzes, collect homework, keep a grade book, and do a variety of other things. In the teaching of English as a second language, communication skill development has expanded. HEMIS is a strong and diverse LMS that administrators may completely administer. The activities of students can be recorded in logs so that professors can subsequently review what they have done on HEMIS and have complete control over the due date and timing for assignments, including tests, forums, chats, and other forms of communication. The use of technological tools is necessary for surviving in a world that is increasingly globalized and technologically advanced. We currently live in the 21st century, which is mostly known for the enormous amount of information that is available in technology-based data, it is essential that we are prepared with these tools not only in our daily lives but also in our academic pursuits. Having stated that, the challenging aspect of this study is primarily to address the implementation of HEMIS and how it might help students in higher education in Nukus learn foreign languages effectively. The study will concentrate on how happy the students are using education management system to learn foreign languages as well. The following questions are addressed by the current study:

- How motivated are the students to the HEMIS be implemented in the tertiary education?
- How might this system help users in the learning and teaching process ??
- How satisfied are the students with using HEMIS?

The following are the precise goals that this study seeks to achieve:

- to investigate the HEMIS application utilized by Nukus State pedagogical institute students.
- to look into how HEMIS might aid in successful foreign language acquisition.
- to determine the level of student satisfaction with using education management system in higher education.

The goal of using a questionnaire is to gather quantitative data. In order to receive as many replies as possible, it was constructed using Survey Monkey app and sent to students of the English Department via social media like Telegram.

Table 1. Usefulness of HEMIS

	Frequency	Percentage
Always	36	37.9%
Usually	41	43.2%
Sometimes	18	18.9%
Never	0	0%
Total	95	100%

In a total of 95 respondents, all the participants have claimed that 95 people responded to the survey, and every one of them admitted to using education management system to further their education. With a total of 41 participants and a percentage of 43.2% of the population, the item "Usually" has received the most votes, followed by the item "Always" with a total of 37.9%. "Sometimes" received the lowest score, with a percentage of 18.9%, indicating that few learners reckon that this education management system is beneficial in learning.

Table 2. Using HEMIS in learning is convenient.

	Frequency	Percentage
Always	29	30.5%
Usually	40	42.1%
Sometimes	25	26.3%
Never	1	1.1%
Total	95	100%

With a rate of 42.1%, most students have stated that they typically feel at ease using this system. A total of 30.5% of respondents said they always feel at ease using education management system, while 26.3% said they only occasionally feel at ease. Amazingly, just one participant selected "Never," indicating that students view HEMIS as convenient and pleasant ways to utilize.

Table 3. Utilizing HEMIS is enjoyable.

	Frequency	Percentage
Always	26	27.4%
Usually	38	40.0%
Sometimes	24	25.3%
Never	7	7.4%
Total	95	100%

The responses to the question "Do you enjoy using HEMIS in the learning process?" are shown in Table 3. Depending on how frequently they enjoy utilizing the system, participants had options ranging from Always to Never. A total of 26 respondents who checked "Always" make up 27.4% of the population, 38 respondents say they typically like using this in the learning process, 24 respondents chose "Sometimes"; and only 7 respondents, or 7.4%, said they never like using.

Table 4 Students' Satisfaction with the use of HEMIS in language learning

Degree of satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfied	29	30.5%
Satisfied	62	65.3%
Unsatisfied	5	5.3%
Total	95	100%

The information in Table 5 above summarizes the responses to the query intended to gauge participants' satisfaction with the use of HEMIS in foreign language learning. The statistical analysis of the data clearly demonstrates that 65.3% of participants are happy with how the system works. Only 5 out of 95 respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the usage of an education management system in advancing their second language proficiency, compared to the greatest degree of satisfaction reported by 30.5% of respondents.

Summary. According to the results of the survey, 41 students out of 95 mentioned that they usually find HEMIS useful and 26 users find always find HEMIS enjoyable, 38 users usually find it enjoyable. Implementation of HEMIS is preferable in comparison with the ex form of management system according to over 50% students. Over 65% students are satisfied with the implementation of HEMIS in learning, likewise, 30% users are very satisfied, whilst only 5% students are unsatisfied with the implementation of this system because of it requires the internet to be able to utilize the system. Students of the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute have shown that the HEMIS as a crucial and beneficial tool and prefer it over the prior management system. Their explanations state that this education management system is practical and potentially beneficial. It enables its users to feel at ease while learning. The summary of the responses indicates inferentially how eager learners are to use HEMIS in the learning process by noting all these.

References:

1. Carol Fallon "E-learning standards" 2002, 45-56
2. Kadirova . L.A Implementation of learning management systems and its role in the educational process in the Republic of Uzbekistan . galaxy international Interdisciplinary Research journal , 2-3 , 2022
3. Rahman, M. J. A., Daud, M. Y., & Ensimau, N. K. Learning Management System (LMS) in Teaching and Learning. International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social sciences 2019, 34-48
4. Salimovna. F "Improving the structure and model interaction of information processes on distance learning", International Journal of advanced trends in computer science and engineering, volume 9, 4043-4048, June 2020
5. Yakubovich, Y. O., & Tohirovna, I. N Doniyor, A., Nastarin, I., N. The role of innovation and use of methods in English teaching . Journal of new century innovations, 27(1), 61-63. 2023